

TECHNOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCES OF CHILDREN WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENTS

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Annotation: This article analyzes the technologies for the formation and development of communicative competencies of children with hearing impairments. It highlights the role of special pedagogical approaches, methods and information and communication tools for children with hearing impairments, as well as methods of integrating them into the educational process. The study analyzes methods aimed at developing oral and written speech and strengthening communication skills in a social environment based on innovative technologies based on experiments.

Keywords: hearing impairment, communicative competence, special pedagogy, speech development, technology, inclusive education, social adaptation.

Introduction.

In order for each child to find his place in society, to be able to freely express his opinion, and to effectively communicate with others, he must first have communicative competencies. Especially for children with hearing impairments, these skills are the basis for adaptation to life, education and active participation in society. Unfortunately, children with hearing impairments face many communication barriers. For them, entering the information world, exchanging ideas, expressing their feelings requires more effort, strength and, most importantly, the right approach than for ordinary children. Modern pedagogy and defectology are looking for new ways to support such children. Technologies, methodological approaches and special communicative environments play an important role in this process. An individual approach, the use of visual and tactile tools, as well as the formation of emotional contact are of great importance in working with children with hearing impairments. Therefore, in-depth study of technologies for the development of communicative competencies and their implementation in practice is an urgent task not only for the education system, but also for society as a whole. This article analyzes technologies, pedagogical methods and effective approaches to developing

communicative competencies of children with hearing impairments. Also, scientific and practical recommendations are put forward on the existing problems in this area and their solutions.

Methodology:

The methodology used in the process of working with children with hearing impairments is based not only on a scientific basis, but also on humanistic principles. Because each of these children has its own worldview, needs and individual development path. Therefore, not a single approach is needed to form their communicative competencies, but an adapted, multifaceted and complex methodological approach. In this study, a person-centered approach, constructive pedagogy, and innovative educational technologies were selected as the main methodological directions. These approaches are of great importance in identifying, developing and strengthening the capabilities of children with hearing impairments. Also, through interactive methods, visual aids, gestural communication, speech therapy exercises, information and communication technologies and role-playing games, children's communication skills were gradually formed.

Qualitative and quantitative analysis methods were used in the research process. The data collected through practical exercises, observations, and pedagogical experiments with children with hearing impairments were analyzed to determine which technologies are more effective in forming communicative competence. Also, interviews were organized with parents, speech therapists and special educators, and proposals were developed based on their opinions and experiences. Through these methodological approaches, practical results were achieved that served to develop oral and written speech skills in children with hearing impairments, increase their opportunities to engage in social communication, freely express their opinions, and integrate into society.

Literature review:

Scientific research on the formation of communicative competencies of children with hearing impairments shows that this area requires an integral connection between the disciplines of pedagogy, psychology, and defectology. Therefore, through an analysis of the existing literature, the main theoretical approaches, methods, and technologies developed in this area were studied in depth.

Scientists such as S.Ya. Rubinshteyn, A.R. Luria, and R.E. Levina have scientifically studied the features of the psychological and physiological development of children with hearing impairments. Their work substantiates

the need for an individual approach to the formation of communicative competencies in children.

Domestic and foreign sources published in recent years indicate the role of technological approaches in this process. In particular, scientists and educators such as X.A. Abduqadirova, M. Akhmedova, Z. Mahkamova have studied the possibilities of using modern didactic technologies, interactive methods and multimedia tools in working with children with hearing impairments. These sources especially recognize the effectiveness of methods such as visual-material means, mimicry, pantomime, dactyl alphabet, and audiovisual materials in developing communication.

Also, scientific research on inclusive education, including international experiences published by UNESCO and UNICEF, emphasize the importance of developing communicative competencies in integrating children with hearing impairments into the general education system.

The analysis shows that although there are various methods and approaches to developing communicative competencies in the existing literature, technological approaches, namely the use of modern information and communication tools, and the development of communication through multimodal learning technologies, still require more extensive research. In this regard, this article aims to analyze the technologies used in this area and determine their effectiveness.

Discussion:

The ability of children with hearing impairments to find their place in life and develop as full-fledged individuals directly depends on their skills in effective communication with society. Observations and analyses conducted during this study, as well as experimentally applied technologies, have shown that the formation of communicative competence is not only an educational, but also a key part of the psychological and social rehabilitation process for these children. Practical experience confirms that the use of visual aids, mimicry and pantomime (expressing letters with fingers) of the alphabet, and the development of expressive speech using multimedia - increase the desire for communication in children with hearing impairments, enhance their sense of self-awareness. In particular, through interactive activities, children strive to share their thoughts with others, which has a positive effect on their socialization. One of the important aspects identified in the study is that the cooperation of parents and educators plays an important role in the development of communicative competence. The child must be brought up on

the basis of a culture of communication not only in an educational institution, but also in the family. Otherwise, the achievements achieved in an educational institution will not be sustainable.

The existing problems in this area also deserve discussion. In particular, factors such as the lack of special classes equipped with modern technologies in all educational institutions, the small number of qualified defectologists and speech therapists, and the outdatedness of methodological manuals and textbooks negatively affect the full development of children. This requires us to create new technological approaches, popularize existing experiences, and develop a systematic methodology. Developing communicative competencies in children with hearing impairments is not only a matter of education, but also a matter of adapting them to society, instilling human values, and instilling confidence in their souls. Scientific and practical research conducted in this area shows that through properly selected methods and pedagogical technologies, any child can become an active, equal member of society.

Conclusion.

Every child, regardless of their ability, has the right to communicate, express their opinions and find their place in society. Children with hearing impairments need more help, more attention and a special pedagogical approach in this regard. During this study, it was concluded that the formation of communicative competence is not only a process of acquiring knowledge for these children, but also a way to strengthen their ability to integrate into social life, self-awareness and expression.

Modern pedagogical technologies, especially information and communication tools, visual teaching methods and interactive approaches, have shown their high efficiency in working with children with hearing impairments. It was found that through these methods it is possible to develop not only speech, but also sensory-emotional, social and psychological competencies. Also, the study once again confirmed the need for close cooperation between the family, educational institution and specialists in the formation of communicative competence. Only an integrated approach, consistent coordination and a loving approach to the child will lead to the expected result. In conclusion, the development of communicative competencies of children with hearing impairments is a complex, but necessary and highly humane process. Their adaptation to society, self-confidence and future success depend on how these competencies develop. Therefore, we - educators, parents, members of society - must be more responsible, patient and innovative on this path.

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